

Abnormal grain growth and functional properties of BaTiO₃ prepared by rapid sintering

methods

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Abstract

The demand for faster sintering methods is increasing due to the need for energy-efficient processing of advanced ceramics. BaTiO₃, a key lead-free electroceramic, presents a challenge due to its microstructure being prone to abnormal grain growth. This study compares sintering of BaTiO₃ using conventional pressure-assisted and pressureless spark plasma sintering, and rapid pressureless sintering. All methods produced tetragonal BaTiO₃ samples with a relative density above 99 %. Abnormal grain growth occurred over temperature intervals narrower than 50 °C in the rapid sintering techniques, compared to 100 °C in conventional sintering. The onset temperature difference was attributed to different energy-transfer mechanisms and the presence of applied pressure. A trade-off was observed between dielectric and piezoelectric performance in relation to microstructural evolution. These results demonstrate the ability of fast pressureless sintering techniques to densify BaTiO₃ in minutes, while providing tunable properties and significant time and energy savings without restrictions on shape.

Keywords

Barium titanate; piezoceramics; pressureless spark plasma sintering; rapid pressureless sintering; microstructure

1 Introduction

Barium titanate (BaTiO_3) is a lead-free electroceramic material whose dielectric, ferroelectric, and piezoelectric properties make it increasingly popular for use in industrial applications such as sensors, capacitors, and energy storage and harvesting systems [1–4]. The electrical properties of BaTiO_3 can be significantly affected by its microstructure, having an optimal response for an intermediate grain size of $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$ [5]. However, titanates are susceptible to abnormal grain growth (AGG)[6]. AGG can be caused by a liquid phase on grain boundaries (GB) [7–10] when the sintering temperature is above the eutectic temperature of $1332 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ of BaTiO_3 - $\text{Ba}_6\text{Ti}_{17}\text{O}_{40}$ system [11]. Below the eutectic temperature, faceted GBs (atomically smooth) can migrate via the step growth mechanism [12]. This process is aided by the emergence of $\{111\}$ double twins, which facilitate preferential sites for rapid grain growth [13]. The grain growth rate transition has been observed between 1275 and $1325 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [14]. As a result, uncontrolled microstructure coarsening occurs and adversely affects the electrical and mechanical properties of BaTiO_3 samples [5]. For this reason, special attention should be given to the microstructural evolution during the sintering of BaTiO_3 ceramics

Conventional pressureless or two-step sintering, involving slow heating rates and prolonged dwell times, can take tens of hours to achieve required density [15,16]. In today's increasingly demanding environment, these methods appear unsustainable. Rapid sintering techniques, employing heating rates above $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and dwell times of only a few minutes, offer an effective alternative. They enable improved microstructural control by limiting the total energy input into the system, while significantly reducing overall energy consumption and carbon footprint through shorter sintering cycles [17].

Another benefit of using rapid heating rates lies in the high densification achieved by these methods. A classical theory explains this by densification-promoting mechanisms of surface diffusion inhibition (via skipping the initial stage of sintering) and immediate activation of

densifying lattice and GB diffusion regimes [18,19]. However, more recent reports tend to disprove the role of surface diffusion inhibition [20] and emphasise the importance of GB structure and composition change under high heating rates [21,22].

Combining high heating rates with applied pressure in Spark plasma sintering (SPS) appears to be the most direct method for obtaining fully dense BaTiO₃ with a fine microstructure [23–28]. However, recent developments in alternative sintering methods, such as pressureless spark plasma sintering (p-SPS)[29–32] and rapid pressureless sintering (RPLS)[25,33–36], offer an alternative approach to ceramic densification without the drawbacks of SPS, which include processing of a single sample at a time and shape constrictions of the final product. This limitation becomes particularly pronounced in the context of using pressure-assisted sintering methods for unique and design-demanding piezoceramics, such as those produced through the evolving field of additive manufacturing.

This study investigates the fast pressureless sintering techniques for rapid consolidation of BaTiO₃ ceramics using p-SPS, SPS, and RPLS with a heating rate of 100 °C/min across various temperatures, with conventional sintering (CS) serving as a benchmark. The primary objective is to achieve high-density samples while identifying the key factors that govern microstructural evolution in fast sintering processes. Furthermore, the relationship between microstructure and ferroelectric domain behaviour, and its influence on electrical properties, is examined in detail.

2 Experimental

2.1 Powders and powder consolidation

Commercial tetragonal BaTiO₃ (particle size 280 nm, Nanografi, Turkey) powder used for p-SPS, RPLS, and CS was mixed with a 3 wt. % of polyethylene glycol binder ($M_n = 200$, Sigma Aldrich, USA) and wet milled in ethanol on a roller bench for 24 h using 5 mm ZrO₂ balls as the milling medium. The powder was then dried, ground in an agate mortar, and sieved through a 500 μm mesh. The powder (6 g) was compacted into pellets using a BSML21 uniaxial press (Brio Hranice, Czech Republic) in a 30 mm die at a pressure of 15 MPa. Further compaction was achieved by cold isostatic pressing at 300 MPa in a KIP 300 E (P/O/Webber, Germany). Powder for SPS was used without an organic binder.

2.2 Heat treatment

The green bodies were calcined in an air atmosphere to remove the organic binder at 800 °C for 1 h in a muffle furnace (Clasic, Czech Republic). p-SPS was performed in an SPS furnace Dr. Sinter 615E (SPS Syntex, Japan). The calcined green bodies were sintered in a graphite crucible with a 60 mm inner diameter, a wall thickness of 4 mm, and a height of 60 mm. Two green bodies were placed on insulating graphite felt at the bottom of the crucible for each run. The temperature was measured using a pyrometer aimed at a 2 mm hole on the outer wall of the crucible. The setup is described in more detail elsewhere [30]. A 10-minute preheating heated the samples above 600 °C. Afterwards, a 100 °C/min heating rate was applied until reaching the sintering temperature in the range of 1325–1400 °C with a dwell of 5 min, followed by a 100 °C/min cooling rate.

RPLS samples were sintered in a superkanthal elevator furnace with a vertically moving sample holder (Clasic, Czech Republic). The experimental setup is described in greater detail elsewhere [33]. The sintering regime involved a heating and cooling rates of 100 °C/min, with a 5 min dwell at temperatures of 1225–1325 °C.

CS samples were sintered in a superkanthal furnace (Clasic, Czech Republic) using heating and cooling rates of 10 °C/min and 120 min dwell at temperatures between 1225 and 1325 °C.

SPS samples were prepared by placing 9.7 g of BaTiO₃ powder into a 30 mm graphite die. A larger amount of powder was used to ensure a similar thickness in the sintered samples as in those prepared by pressureless methods from pressed green bodies. Sintering was performed in the SPS furnace Dr. Sinter 615E (SPS Syntex, Japan). The samples were first heated above 600 °C with a 10-minute preheating, during which a pressure of 50 MPa was gradually reached. The sintering temperature in the 1225–1325 °C range was then reached at a 100 °C/min heating rate, followed by a 5 min dwell. The pressure was gradually released during cooling at a rate of 100 °C/min. The SPS and p-SPS samples were then annealed in an air atmosphere in a muffle furnace (Clasic, Czech Republic) at 1000 °C for 24 h to remove any possible carbon contamination and the effects of the reductive atmosphere in the SPS-based processes that take place in the presence of graphite and vacuum. The sintering regimes and sample designation are summarised in Table 1.

2.3 Analyses

The relative density of the sintered samples was measured using the Archimedes method (EN 18754). The theoretical density (TD) of BaTiO₃ used for calculations was 6.02 g/cm³. The microstructure was observed using a Mira3 scanning electron microscope (SEM, Tescan, Czech Republic) in both secondary electron (SE) and backscatter electron mode (BSE). The mean grain size (MGS) was measured on SEM micrographs of polished and thermally etched (100 °C below the sintering temperature) surfaces using the linear intercept method with a correction factor of 1.56 [37]. The domain width was measured on SEM micrographs of polished surfaces that were chemically etched by a mixture of 95 ml distilled H₂O, 3 ml HCl, and 2 ml HF to reveal the ferroelectric domain structure. To show how properties depend on

the microstructure, a single value of effective grain size was calculated, due to bimodal distribution of grain sizes in some samples, according to the Equation 1:

$$GS_{eff} = f_{fine}MGS_{fine} + f_{coarse}MGS_{coarse}, (1)$$

where GS_{eff} is the effective grain size, f_{fine} and f_{coarse} are the area fractions of fine and coarse grains, and MGS_{fine} and MGS_{coarse} are their respective mean grain sizes.

Phase composition was analysed by an X-ray powder diffractometer SmartLab 3kW (XRD, Rigaku, Japan) in the Bragg-Brentano setup using a Cu-K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). Data processing and Rietveld refinement were performed using PDXL2 software (Rigaku, Japan).

Prior to poling, silver (Ag) paste was applied to the samples, followed by firing at 700 °C for 10 minutes. Small-signal converse piezoelectric constant d_{33}^* (pm/V, sine wave function; 50 V; 1 kHz) was measured using a piezoelectric evaluation system (aixPES, aixACCT Systems, Germany) on unpoled samples. The quasi-static piezoelectric constant, d_{33} (pC/N), was measured by a Berlincourt d_{33} meter (ZJ-3C, Institute of Physics, China) after poling in silicon oil at 2 kV/mm for 30 min at 100 °C.

Table 1 Sample designation and their respective sintering cycles.

Sintering method	Sample	Sintering temp. [°C]/dwell [min]
p-SPS*	p-SPS1325	1325/5
	p-SPS1350	1350/5
	p-SPS1375	1375/5
	p-SPS1400	1400/5
SPS*	SPS1225	1225/5
	SPS1250	1250/5
	SPS1275	1275/5
	SPS1300	1300/5
	SPS1325	1325/5
RPLS	RPLS1225	1225/5
	RPLS1250	1250/5
	RPLS1275	1275/5
	RPLS1300	1300/5
	RPLS1325	1325/5
CS	CS1225	1225/120
	CS1250	1250/120
	CS1275	1275/120
	CS1300	1300/120
	CS1325	1325/120

*post-annealed at 1000 °C for 24 hours in an air atmosphere

3 Results

3.1 Phase composition

The XRD diffractograms of p-SPS samples (Fig. 1a) show the exclusive presence of BaTiO₃. The samples were not fully tetragonal BaTiO₃ (*t*-BaTiO₃), as indicated in Fig. 1a by the percentage of *t*-BaTiO₃. The remaining phase was cubic BaTiO₃ (*c*-BaTiO₃), which is sometimes referred to as pseudo-cubic [38], and was studied in detail by examining the peaks around 45° 2θ (Fig. 1b). This shows that the typical *t*-BaTiO₃ peak splitting was present in all sintered samples with two distinct peaks: a lower-intensity (002) peak doublet (Kα₁ and Kα₂) followed by a higher-intensity (200) peak doublet. However, the splitting was often imperfect, and a less intense cubic peak (200) was also present between the tetragonal peaks. The *c*-BaTiO₃ content generally decreased with increasing sintering temperature in all the studied sintering techniques. Similarly, the *c/a* ratio (tetragonality, noted in Fig. 1b) of the *t*-BaTiO₃ phase increased with increasing sintering temperature, which is consistent with the literature [24,39,40]. Diffractograms for SPS, RPLS, and CS samples have shown similar trends in the increasing share and tetragonality of the *t*-BaTiO₃ phase and can be found in the Supplemental information as Fig. S1, S2, and S3, respectively. The sole exception to this trend was the sample RPLS1300, which showed a slight decrease in *t*-BaTiO₃ content compared to RPLS1275, but then increased again to 100 % in the sample RPLS1325. For the full quantification table with *c/a* ratios, see Supplemental Table S1.

Fig. 1 X-ray diffraction patterns of a) p-SPS samples showing the amount of tetragonal phase and b) enlarged view of the peaks at $2\theta \approx 45^\circ$ with marked (002) and (200) peaks of tetragonal BaTiO₃ and its c/a ratio shown in brackets.

3.2 Density

Uniaxial pressing followed by CIP resulted in ceramic green bodies with a relative density of 61.8 ± 0.1 % of TD. Subsequently, all selected sintering techniques produced samples with high relative density at or above 99 % of TD (see Fig. 2). p-SPS reached this densification level at the higher sintering temperatures (1375 and 1400 °C). SPS produced samples with the highest densities consistently across the entire range of sintering temperatures. Similarly, RPLS samples achieved relative densities between 98.5 and 99 % of TD across selected sintering temperatures. Finally, CS led to samples approaching 99 % of TD above 1250 °C. For the whole table, see Supplemental Table S2. The reason for the higher sintering temperatures in p-SPS samples is explained in Section 4.1.

Fig. 2 Dependence of relative density on sintering temperature of samples prepared by various sintering techniques.

3.3 Microstructure

SEM micrographs (see Fig. 3) show the microstructural evolution for all sintering techniques, presented in respective rows, starting with a fine-grained microstructure, followed by an image of equiaxed coarse grains among fine grains (AGG), and finally, a coarse-grained microstructure with several grains containing $\{111\}$ twinning planes (white arrows).

Fig. 3 SEM micrographs of a) p-SPS1325, b) p-SPS1375, c) p-SPS1400, d) SPS1225, e) SPS1250, f) SPS1300, g) RPLS1225, h) RPLS1250, i) RPLS1275, j) CS1225, k) CS1275, and l) CS1325, all in BSE mode. Black arrows mark remaining clusters of fine grains, and white arrows indicate twinning. Note different scalebars.

Fig. 4 shows the MGS of finer and coarser grain populations, along with their respective shares within the microstructure, which is fully listed in the Supplemental Information, Table S2. Annealing at 1000 °C had no apparent effect on the microstructure of the p-SPS and SPS samples, with the MGS and AGG remaining unchanged from those of the as-sintered samples.

Fig. 4 The MGS of fine (circles) and coarse-grain (hollow squares) populations. The shaded area marks the percentage of coarse grains in the microstructure. The colours represent the sintering techniques used.

Grains of p-SPS samples were $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$ at 1325 °C and 1350 °C, the latter with less than 1 % of the area consisting of isolated coarse grains. An increase of 25 °C led to abrupt AGG, and p-SPS1375 consisted of a majority of coarse grains $\approx 40 \mu\text{m}$. At 1400 °C, fine grains disappeared, and coarse grains exceeded 60 μm . SPS samples sintered at 1225–1275 °C had $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$ fine-grained microstructure (see Fig. 3d) but also contained clusters of enlarged grains, mainly concentrated around larger pores (see Fig. 3e). To our knowledge, this is the first report of similar microstructural features. The clusters accounted for the less than 4 % across the 1225–1275 °C sintering temperature range and started to appear even at lower temperatures of 1150 °C (not included in the study). Their formation can be attributed to progressive

compaction and necking, which establish conductive percolation paths; localized Joule heating along these paths then promotes grain coarsening [41,42].

AGG occurred between 1275 and 1300 °C, and as a result, the SPS1300 microstructure was almost entirely coarse ($\approx 60 \mu\text{m}$) with a few fine-grained areas (indicated by black arrows, Fig. 3f). Sample SPS1325 consisted only of coarse grains with MGS of $78 \mu\text{m}$.

A similar microstructural evolution was observed in the RPLS samples. RPLS1225 had a fine-grained microstructure (Fig. 3g), RPLS1250 exhibited AGG and coarse grains over $60 \mu\text{m}$ formed 50 % of the cross-section (Fig. 3h), and RPLS1275 consisted of over 99 % coarse grains below $60 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 3i). MGS of original fine grains rose from $1.1 \mu\text{m}$ (RPLS1225) to $1.9 \mu\text{m}$ (RPLS1275). In comparison, the coarse grains were gradually smaller, starting at $69 \mu\text{m}$ in the case of RPLS1250 and decreasing to $41 \mu\text{m}$ in RPLS1325. Finally, CS exhibited the fine-grained microstructure in the CS1225 sample (Fig. 3j), and AGG gradually appeared at higher sintering temperatures. CS1250 sample contained over 11 % of coarse grains which further increased to 52 % in sample CS1275 (Fig. 3k), 87 % in sample CS1300, and finally 100 % in sample CS1325 (Fig. 3l). While the size of the fine grain population increased from 1.2 to $1.6 \mu\text{m}$, the observed coarse grains were above $100 \mu\text{m}$, the largest of all the used sintering methods.

3.4 Ferroelectric domains

After the chemical etching of polished cross-sections of unpoled samples, SEM observations revealed the ferroelectric domains. Fig. 5 shows examples of domain structures obtained by each sintering method (Fig. 5a-d) and details of a coarse grain (Fig. 5e) and fine grains (Fig. 5f). Several types of domain patterns in coarse grains were identified, including the watermarks, herringbones, and stripes.

Fig. 5 SEM micrographs in SE mode of the domain structure of samples a) p-SPS1350, b) SPS1300, c) RPLS1250, d) CS1300, and details of e) coarse-grain domains in the CS1300 sample and f) fine-grain domains in the SPS1250 sample. Note different scalebars.

Domains in fine grains were comparable in size, regardless of the sintering method, ranging between 0.15 and 0.41 μm . However, samples with coarse grains offered a more interesting insight. Individual coarse grains typically contained several intragranular domain structures, each comprised of almost identical domains (see examples in Fig. 5a-e). However, each domain structure varied significantly within a single grain and generally increased with increasing grain size. To avoid the effect of other coarse grains impinging on the domain structure and the grain size, domain width was measured in individual isolated coarse grains of various sizes surrounded by fine grains (an example is in Fig. 5c). The measured width was plotted against the square root of grain size (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Dependence of domain width on the square root of the grain size of individual abnormal grains surrounded only by fine microstructure. Each grain's upper, lower, and mean domain widths are shown.

3.5 Electrical properties

The samples' relative permittivity (ϵ_r) exhibited a similar trend across all sintering methods. Lower temperatures, and thus smaller grain size, resulted in values over 2700 for RPLS and CS with higher values over 3000 for p-SPS and even approaching 3500 for the SPS1250 sample (Fig. 7a). The increase in the sintering temperature led to a decrease of ϵ_r by roughly 50 % for all sintering methods, as the mean grain size increased. Loss coefficient $\tan \delta$ was close to zero for all samples, ranging between 0.05 and 0.01 with no significant trend (Fig. 7a). When plotted against the effective grain size (Fig. 7b), calculated according to the Equation 1, ϵ_r tended to decrease with grain size, following the same trend as with the sintering temperature.

Fig. 7 Dependence of ϵ_r and $\tan \delta$ on a) sintering temperature and b) effective grain size (of bimodal grain size distributions), and dependence of d_{33}^* [pm/V] and d_{33} [pC/N] on c) sintering temperature and d) effective grain size of samples sintered by different techniques.

The piezoelectric response of the studied samples showed the opposite trend. For all used sintering methods, higher sintering temperatures increased the piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} measured by the Berlincourt method [pC/N] and as a small signal converse piezoelectric coefficient d_{33}^* [pm/V], see Fig. 7c. The coefficient rose from values around 100 pm/V to well over 200 pm/V and even reached 291 pm/V in the sample RPLS1325 sintered by RPLS. Lower values, but with similar trends, were observed for directly measured d_{33} . Similarly, piezoelectric performance rose with effective grain size (Fig. 7d), with the exception of d_{33} in RPLS samples, where it actually declined beyond the sample RPLS1325 with $\approx 40 \mu\text{m}$ grains

(see hollow cyan squares in Fig. 7d). For the full table with ϵ_r , $\tan \delta$, and d_{33} coefficients, see Supplemental information, Table S3.

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4 Discussion

4.1 The densification of BaTiO₃ by different sintering strategies and mechanisms

All sintering routes used in this study achieved high densification, with relative densities at or above 99 % of TD, levels that are rarely reported for pressureless BaTiO₃, which typically remain below 98 % of TD [25,43–48]. Higher density of our CS samples may be attributed to the fine starting powder driving densification or the high packing density and homogeneity of green bodies obtained by CIP. Pressure-assisted sintering, which employs additional densification mechanisms, such as plastic deformation and grain boundary sliding in addition to relying on densification through GB and lattice diffusion, is usually necessary to reach densities above 99 % of TD [25–28]. Our SPS samples achieved these values across all sintering temperatures. Finally, p-SPS and RPLS, unconventional pressureless sintering methods strongly employing the radiative heat transfer, also produced nearly fully dense samples. This was achieved despite their lack of pressure, short dwell times of 5 min, and high heating and cooling rates of 100 °C/min. The latter were shown to positively influence the densification, likely by limiting non-densifying surface diffusion or through variations in GB structure and composition at high heating rates [18,19,21,33,49].

However, p-SPS required over 100 °C higher sintering temperature compared to other methods. A recent report by Kocjan *et al.* [30] showed with finite element modelling (FEM) that the sample (3Y-TZP zirconia ceramics, identical furnace configuration) during p-SPS is exposed to ≈ 120 °C lower temperature than what is measured on the crucible wall due to the lack of direct contact. In contrast, in the SPS configuration, where the sample directly contacts the graphite die, the simulated and experimental temperatures agreed. The 120 °C correction was applied to the p-SPS relative density data (see Fig. 1Fig. 8a), which now show close similarity of the densities to those of other sintering methods.

Fig. 8 The outcome of the FEM correction [29] of the p-SPS temperature on a) the relative density of samples prepared using various sintering techniques and b) the percentage of coarse grains in the microstructure.

Taking this into account, all sintering routes used in this study (p-SPS, SPS, RPLS, and CS) showed the capability to fully densify BaTiO₃. However, the sintering routes differ in their heat-transfer mechanisms: CS proceeds through conduction and convection, RPLS and p-SPS rely more on radiative heating [21,50], and SPS combines conduction with Joule heating inside the die [42]. The differences observed in the final microstructures therefore arise primarily from different thermal configurations rather than from densification limitations.

4.2 Abnormal grain growth differences

While all sintering techniques produced dense ceramics, they differed in the onset and width of AGG window. The slower heating rate in the case of CS samples likely resulted in grain (pre)coarsening at early stages, which reduced the driving force for AGG [8], and the microstructure transformed gradually over 100 °C. In contrast, the high-heating-rate techniques resulted in much narrower window: 50 °C in p-SPS and RPLS, and 25 °C in SPS. A notable consequence of faster AGG in p-SPS and RPLS, is the higher number of intragranular pores due to the rapid radiation-driven heating causing the GB mobility to exceed the pore mobility (see Fig. 3b, i) [51]. This microstructural feature may also explain why, although the small-signal converse piezoresponse d_{33}^* increased with grain size, the direct piezoelectric

coefficient d_{33} did not follow the same trend, suggesting reduced poling efficiency or mechanical coupling in the RPLS microstructures in particular [52]. Conversely, the slower progress of AGG in CS samples and the applied pressure in SPS samples resulted in far fewer intragranular pores in coarse grains, as shown in Fig. 3f, l.

Although the rate at which AGG progressed varied among the methods, the actual AGG onset temperature was more consistent than it initially appeared. As discussed in Section 4.1, the FEM revealed that the actual sample temperature during p-SPS is approximately 120 °C lower than the temperature measured on the crucible wall [30]. Lower actual temperature of the sample also means that the AGG occurred below the eutectic temperature of 1332 °C [11] and liquid phase-driven secondary AGG can therefore be disregarded [53]. After applying the correction (Fig. 8b), the microstructural evolution of p-SPS and RPLS, both radiation-driven processes, closely overlaps despite their different furnace designs. The AGG in CS, the last studied pressureless sintering technique, also started at the same temperature, although the transition window was wider. The later AGG onset in SPS samples can be attributed to the low oxygen partial pressure in SPS furnace resulting in atomically rough GBs and oxygen vacancies causing normal grain growth [13,42,54], therefore postponing the AGG onset to 1275 °C. However, the AGG in p-SPS started at a temperature ~50 °C lower (after the FEM correction). This suggests that the influence of the sintering atmosphere in SPS-based processes was likely outweighed by other processing variables, such as lower porosity in SPS samples, which reduces GB pinning; once a critical temperature was reached, the AGG could then proceed abruptly [9,55].

Abnormal grain growth in BaTiO₃ is governed by the balance between faceted GB mobility, pore drag, and to limited extent, twinning [12]. However, {111} twin double-planes were observed only in some of the coarse grains and therefore can be disregarded as the dominant driving mechanism of AGG in equiaxed grains of stoichiometric BaTiO₃ [14]. The relative

strength of these driving forces is governed by the energy-transfer mechanism of each sintering method and the presence of external pressure. Our results demonstrate that neither absolute temperature, sintering atmosphere, nor heating rate alone accounts for the observed differences in microstructures.

4.3 Domains and electrical properties

The microstructure influences electrical performance through changes in domain wall density, mobility, and the switching behaviour of non-180° domain walls. Domain wall density is closely linked to domain size, which as our observations confirmed (Fig. 6), increases with square root of grain size [56]. The ideal domain wall density for high relative permittivity ϵ_r is achieved at grain sizes $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$ [5]. Reported ϵ_r followed the expected behaviour [57–60]: regardless of the sintering method, ϵ_r decreased from the 2500–3500 range down to 1500–2000, as the microstructures coarsened due to AGG.

As the microstructure coarsened above $\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$, the lamellar domain structure characteristic of fine grains transformed into more complex configurations, such as watermarks (180° domain walls), herringbones (90° and 180° domain walls), and stripes (90° domain walls) [61,62]. The formation of complex domain structures originated from the lower density of GBs in coarse-grained microstructure [56]. This, in turn, reduced the elastic stresses that constrain the mobility and switching of non-180° domain walls [63,64], resulting in a higher remnant polarisation P_r in the coarse-grained BaTiO₃ [9,56]. Therefore, the GBs can have detrimental effect on ferroelectric and piezoelectric properties.

Consequently, coarse-grained samples exhibited higher d_{33} (see Fig. 7d). The d_{33} rose when measured by the Berlincourt method and also as a small signal converse piezoelectric coefficient d_{33}^* . This behaviour contradicts some literature reports, where d_{33} should peak at a similar grain size ($\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$) as ϵ_r [5,57,58,60]. However, several studies also support the opposite view. Wang *et al.* [63] showed that, based on the starting powders, d_{33} could both decrease and

increase with increasing grain size. Two of the characterised materials exhibited increasing d_{33} up to their maximal grain sizes of 60 μm . Tan *et al.* [65] reported that SPS-processed BaTiO_3 with grain sizes between 1 and 10 μm , produced the highest value of 432 pC/N in the sample with 4.3 μm grains. Similarly, d_{33} values as high as 480 pC/N are reported for BaTiO_3 ceramic with 5.6–11.3 μm grain size prepared with a hydrothermally synthesised BaTiO_3 fine powder by hot-press sintering [52]. Another contributing factor for the increase in d_{33} might be the higher tetragonality of samples sintered at higher temperatures, see Section 3.1. Our results show that the electrical properties of BaTiO_3 are controlled not by the sintering method itself but by the microstructural evolution each method imposes, linking the specific sintering conditions to AGG behaviour, domain configuration, and finally, electrical performance.

5 Conclusions

All of the rapid sintering methods used produced tetragonal BaTiO₃ and with relative densities above 99 % of the theoretical density, matching or even surpassing the results obtained using conventional sintering methods. However, the width of abnormal grain growth window was different: 100 °C for conventional sintering, 50 °C for pressureless spark plasma sintering and rapid pressureless sintering, and 25 °C for spark plasma sintering. This demonstrates the potential to control microstructural evolution by choosing a particular sintering method. Furthermore, a comparison of the sintering techniques revealed that neither the absolute temperature nor the heating rate alone accounts for the differences in the onset of abnormal grain growth. Rather, the observed shift originates from distinct energy-transfer mechanisms and the presence of applied pressure in each configuration. Once the actual sample temperature is corrected for, radiation-dominated techniques behave similarly. Functionally, the samples with a mean grain size of around 1 μm achieved the highest ϵ_r values. Conversely, the piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} increased with grain size, probably due to higher tetragonality, increased domain wall mobility, and easier domain switching. Identifying the thermal-field configuration as the main factor controlling grain growth establishes a framework for tailoring the microstructure and performance of BaTiO₃. Our work has demonstrated that rapid pressureless sintering and pressureless spark plasma sintering have significant potential for substantial energy and time savings compared to conventional sintering, while achieving comparable or superior properties and more versatility to traditional pressure-assisted spark plasma sintering.

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7 Data availability

The datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study are available in the repository [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18233071].

8 Conflict of interest

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

9 Figure captions

Fig. 1 X-ray diffraction patterns of a) p-SPS samples showing the amount of tetragonal phase and b) enlarged view of the peaks at $2\theta \approx 45^\circ$ with marked (002) and (200) peaks of tetragonal BaTiO₃ and its c/a ratio shown in brackets.

Fig. 2 Dependence of relative density on sintering temperature of samples prepared by various sintering techniques.

Fig. 3 SEM micrographs of a) p-SPS1325, b) p-SPS1375, c) p-SPS1400, d) SPS1225, e) SPS1250, f) SPS1300, g) RPLS1225, h) RPLS1250, i) RPLS1275, j) CS1225, k) CS1275, and l) CS1325, all in BSE mode. Black arrows mark remaining clusters of fine grains, and white arrows indicate twinning. Note different scalebars.

Fig. 4 The MGS of fine (circles) and coarse-grain (hollow squares) populations. The shaded area marks the percentage of coarse grains in the microstructure. The colours represent the sintering techniques used.

Fig. 5 SEM micrographs in SE mode of the domain structure of samples a) p-SPS1350, b) SPS1300, c) RPLS1250, d) CS1300, and details of e) coarse-grain domains in the CS1300 sample and f) fine-grain domains in the SPS1250 sample. Note different scalebars.

Fig. 6 Dependence of domain width on the square root of the grain size of individual abnormal grains surrounded only by fine microstructure. Each grain's upper, lower, and mean domain widths are shown.

Fig. 7 Dependence of ε_r and $\tan \delta$ on a) sintering temperature and b) effective grain size (of bimodal grain size distributions), and dependence of d_{33}^* [pm/V] and d_{33} [pC/N] on c) sintering temperature and d) effective grain size of samples sintered by different techniques.

Fig. 8 The outcome of the FEM correction [29] of the p-SPS temperature on a) the relative density of samples prepared using various sintering techniques and b) the percentage of coarse grains in the microstructure.

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